

A NEW ROBOTIZED FILAMENT WINDING CELL TO MANUFACTURE COMPLEX SHAPE PARTS

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This work shows a robotized filament winding cell that allows to produce composite parts, characterised by high functional performances, by controlling process parameters: tension fibre, winding trajectory and deposition speed. In order to optimise the winding process, it is necessary to attain the following objects: i) to control and plan the winding trajectories in order to amplify the typology and the complexity of the parts to realize; ii) to maximize the deposition speed, in order to reduce manufacturing times; iii) to control the winding tension, in order to improve the mechanical properties of the parts. With regard to these objects a new cell that consists of an anthropomorphic robot, a fixed support and a unique device including a fiber feed spool, a fiber tensioner and a deposition system, has been realized. The new cell has proved to give better results in all process conditions and to satisfy the acceptable limits established by the well-known aeronautic company. The use of a cell with such characteristics represents an important step for the industrial development of the filament winding technology applied to the manufacturing of complex shapes.

Keywords: robotized filament winding, process parameters control, complex shape parts, industrial applicability.

INTRODUCTION

Filament winding technology is used to manufacture composite parts characterised by a rotational axis by the deposition of a filament on a mandrel, with adequate shape, put on a lathe-like numerically controlled machine. On the contrary parts characterised by a complex 3D geometry are wound by hand. The need for high precision and cost reduction in manufacturing complex 3D parts requires high flexible systems that are easy to programme and to control. [1]

Filament winding is able to manufacture composite parts and is characterised by high repeatability, flexibility and process quality for small batch productions, especially, but not exclusively, for the aerospace industry [2-5]. The properties of a mechanical part are strictly influenced by the manufacturing parameters [6-7]; this implies that parameters should be controlled during each phase of the process, and in particular during the phase previous to curing, the “stratification phase”. In fact, the stratification technique strongly influences the whole manufacturing process. As far as the “stratification phase” of filament winding technology is concerned, the critical process parameters are the roving tension, the deposition speed and the winding trajectory. Roving tension influences composite compactness and, as a consequence, the mechanical properties of the composite part [8-9]. In fact, the higher is the tension value, the larger is the quantity of fibres in a unit of volume (i.e. the fewer are the empty spaces among fibres). If the applied tension is not enough, fibre may present wrinkling or folds along the deposition direction, causing defects in the final composite part (i.e. “marcels”). At the same time a very high tension value may cause both a fibre damaging and a strong inhomogeneous compactness of the roving along the underlying surface. Solving this trade-off means to determine the value of the tension that allows to minimize the empty spaces, the wrinkling and the folds, and to have a component with a good structural uniformity. It is to note that, usually, an incorrect choice of the process parameters does not become evident after the winding, but the defects appear only after the wound product is closed in the compaction tooling and before the final curing operation. The deposition speed can cause vibrations of the robot joints and a difficult roving paying off from the spool induced by the increasing of the deposition speed. In fact, since the fibres are crossed on the spool, the friction among the fibres that are paying off and those still wound on the spool results difficult; so the fibre paying off does not happen in a continuous way. The winding path

determines the quality of composite parts mainly in terms of empty spaces among fibres, but it can also induce errors such as fibre bridging, slippage tendency and fibre torsion [11-13]. The winding path, in connection with the deposition speed, influences the accuracy of the deposition system and therefore, the robot accuracy.

In order to optimise the winding process, it is necessary to attain the following objectives:

- i) to control and plan the winding trajectories in order to enlarge the geometrical range and to increase the complexity of the producible parts;
- ii) to maximise the deposition speed, in order to reduce manufacturing times;
- iii) to carefully control the winding tension, in order to improve the mechanical properties of the parts.

The present work evaluates the performances of a new robotized filament winding cell that allows to produce composite parts characterised by high functional performances. Experimental tests have been carried out for different values of the process parameters by means of design of experiment (D.O.E) techniques. Part compactness and fibre alignment were evaluated by measuring the most critical defects inside part volume or on its boundaries, i.e. marcel, delamination and porosity, wrinkles and pinchings, through non-destructive tests. The new cell has proved to give better results in all process conditions and to satisfy the acceptable limits established by a well-known aeronautic company.

NEW ROBOTIZED FILAMENT WINDING CELL

The new manufacturing cell is composed of an anthropomorphic robot, opportunely equipped with a unique and innovative device and a winding die, shown in Figure 2. The robot is an anthropomorphic Kuka, with 6 d.o.f., payload 45 kg, max. reach: 2041 mm, work envelope volume 24 m³, repeatability $\leq \pm 0.15$ mm.

Figure 2. New robotized filament winding cell

The winding device, already described in previous works [14,15], has been designed and built on the basis of compactness, structural lightness, stiffness and functionality principles, in order to guarantee both the maximum dexterity of the robot, to minimise the probability of crashes between the winding die and the components of the cell, and to improve the control of the process parameters for accuracy and repeatability. The feeding device shows a modular structure, shown in Figure 3, constituted by four critical subgroups or modules: the main frame, the roving-guide system, the roving tensioner and the deposition system.

The winding die is mounted on a circular plate by means of a tie rod. The plate allows to mount the tie rod in different locations as required by the shape of the winding die. The length of the tie rod is reduced in order to avoid collisions during winding.

Figure 3. Feed-deposition device

COMPOSITE PART QUALITY

A composite material is univocally defined by the nature and the properties of its constituents, by the reinforcement geometry and distribution and by the characteristics of the reinforcement-matrix interface. The reinforcement geometry may be defined by a shape, a dimension, a concentration and an orientation inside the matrix. Different orientations and kinds of fibres carry out to different composite mechanical performances.

The quality of parts manufactured in composite material is connected with the presence of defects inside part volume or on its boundary surface. These defects are inevitable, since manufacturing process is very complex; they are due to the different manufacturing steps, such as winding, die closing and curing. To determine a composite part quality, some diagnostic techniques, called non-destructive tests, are used: they map defects distribution inside a part, at the end of the manufacturing process, allowing to define part acceptability.

In aeronautic field, the attention is focused on the following defects: marcel, delaminations, porosity, wrinkles and pinchings. They are function of winding, die closing and curing processes. Once noticed the presence of defects inside a part, the part is not rejected, but it is classified on the basis of defects dimension and distribution. In this way parts are classified into a set of classes characterised by scores increasing (1÷4) with decreasing of part functionality (increasing of defects presence). The scores under 3 value imply to accept the tested part. Therefore, these scores define how much critical is the part defectiveness. They were established on the basis of the experience ripened by manufacturing companies of composite parts. The scores scale was defined in conformity with the aeronautical certification standards; it is the result of a set of fatigue failure tests, measuring functionality changes, carried out on parts with known defects.

Marcel is a fibre buckling that can occurs during winding. It is characterized by a shape ratio, $G=L/R$, where L and R are buckling length and height respectively (see Figure 4). Increasing buckling height and, therefore, worsening part defectiveness, involves decreasing G ratio value. It is possible to classify composite parts on the basis of G ratio. It is possible to obtain different classes characterised by scores increasing with increasing of part defectiveness (see Table 1). The maximum diameter of a circle inscribing marcel cross section has not to exceed 10 mm.

Delamination or debonding is due to the presence of empty spaces at the interface between fibres and matrix without fibre breaking. A part may present one or many empty spaces that are placed in parallel (called multiple delamination), as shown in Figure 5.

A delamination is characterized by the length L and the width D of the area A concerning the empty spaces. If D may be neglected, the delamination is single, otherwise it is multiple. The number and the dimensions of the empty spaces, that render part acceptable, depend on the kind of manufactured part. For example, the benchmark used in aeronautic field and described in the following is considered acceptable if it presents a single longitudinal empty space whose maximum length "L" has a value of about 10mm, while its width D may be considered negligible, as shown in "single delamination" column of Table 2. These conditions correspond to score values less than 3. If the distance among empty spaces is less than 25mm, it has to consider these empty spaces as a single one. Multiple delaminations involve a part acceptable if the length and the width of the empty spaces are no more than 10 mm and 5 mm respectively (see column "Multiple delamination" in Table 2).

Figure 4. Marcel cross-section

Scores scale	Shape ratio $G=L/R$
1	$G \geq 3,7$
2	$2,5 \leq G < 3,7$
3	$2,1 \leq G < 2,5$
4	$G < 2,1$

Figure 5. Multiple delamination

	Single Delamination ($D \approx 0$)	Multiple delamination
Score scale	Length L [mm]	Area A [mm^2]
1	$L \leq 3$	$A \leq 15$
2	$3 < L \leq 7$	$15 < A \leq 30$
3	$7 < L \leq 10$	$30 < A \leq 50$
4	$L > 10$	$A > 50$

Porosity is due to the presence of empty spaces inside part that are caused by a not enough compacting force of the fibres. To quantify this kind of defect is hard, it is based on the comparison of part radiography with a set of radiographic standards that take into account the empty spaces position more than their dimensions. In this way, parts are divided in classes characterised by scores increasing (1÷4) with increasing of porosity and, therefore, increasing of part defectiveness. A part with a score ranging inside 1÷3 is considered acceptable.

Pinchings and wrinkles are defects placed on part boundary. They are due to a wrong mating of the closed die on the winding die. Wrinkles are acceptable if they concern part boundary, while pinching are neglected, since they are removed through glass-paper.

EVALUATION OF NEW CELL PERFORMANCES

The evaluation of the performances of the new cell has involved the investigation of the influence of the process parameters, achievable by the new cell, on the quality of the manufactured parts. The deposition speed and the fibre tension have been considered variable parameters, while the winding trajectory has been considered a fixed parameter. The benchmark and the composite material to use have been chosen, the robot trajectory has been planned and the parts have been controlled and tested. All the details are reported as follows.

Benchmark used for the experimental tests

The benchmark is an irregular ring, shown in Figure 6. It is commonly used by an important Italian aeronautic company to test alternative composites manufacturing technologies and systems [15].

The material is carbon roving impregnated by epoxy resin, conformed to MIL-R-9300 requirements. The slip tape consists of 12 thousand (12K) filament-count tows. Polyacrilonite (PAN) precursor graphite fibres are used. The slip tape has a $3.2 \pm 0.8 \text{ mm}$ width and a $0.76 \div 0.85 \text{ g/m}$ yield.

The part usually requires about 90 revolutions around the supporting die.

Design of the experimental plan

The deposition speed and the fiber tension have been considered as variable parameters. All the values of the two process parameters, allowing not to correctly finish the winding, have been avoided. Moreover, the values of the process parameters have been chosen in such a way to reproduce industrial manufacturing conditions, but even to overcome them by proving economic convenient

combinations. Therefore, for each process parameter a value higher, and more demanding, than industrial one has been used. A set of experimental tests has been designed by means of a factorial experimental plan. The designed plan is given in Table 3. Each test has been replicated three times, yielding a total of 30 manufactured benchmarks. The number of benchmarks actually available for quality investigations has been of about 22, since some combinations of the values of the process parameters shown in Table 3 have not produced three integral benchmarks adapt for the further analyses.

Figure 6. Dimensions (in mm) of the irregular ring benchmark.

Table 3. Experimental plan

Process variables	Number of levels	Values
Deposition speed [mm/min]	2	4000-6000
Roving tension [N]	5	30-50-60-70-90

Replications	3
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Manufactured benchmarks	22
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Determination of the winding trajectory

The winding trajectory has been considered as a fixed variable. It has been defined thanks to the considerations briefly described below and more thoroughly reported in previous publications [17, 18]. If we consider the benchmark previously described (see §4.1), the winding trajectory should fill the whole area of the benchmark section shown in Figure 8 by winding continuously the roving. The composite roving has an approximate rectangular section smaller than the component cross section. It is possible to define two main directions: the first one (called Y) determines the growth of each layer by placing single coils side by side, while the second main direction (called X), perpendicular to the first one, constitutes the direction where the superposition of the layers takes place. The section build-up takes place at first along the Y-axis and then along the X-axis in a continuous way, as shown in Figure 7.

The resulting winding trajectory is constituted by a minimum number of roving positions during its placement on the die, as shown in Figure 8.

Once wound, the irregular rings have been closed between winding and closed dies (Figure 9). Then, they have been placed inside an autoclave to carry out the curing process. Curing conditions have used a heat up rate of $2\div3^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$, a temperature of $125\pm 3^{\circ}\text{C}$ for a time of 90 min, a cool at 60°C .

Finally, the benchmarks have been pulled out the die and they have been deburred and subjected to x-ray non destructive tests in order to identify the defects previously described (see §3).

Figure 7. Benchmark cross-section and winding die (left) and winding sequence (right).

Figure 8. Discretized winding trajectory (left); winding trajectory details with respect to roving orientations (right).

Figure 9. Irregular ring on the winding die (left) and between winding and closed dies (right)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To evaluate the performances of new filament winding cell, the influence of the process parameters, achievable by means of the new cell, on the quality of the manufactured benchmarks has been carried out by a multifactor analysis of variance. The defects, introduced in §3, have been identified and characterized for manufactured benchmarks. The fundamental hypotheses of the ANOVA applicability to the experimental data (residual normality, homogeneity of residuals variance) have been tested. Plots have been used in order to have a graphical image of the response trend.

Marcel shape ratio G seems to significantly depend only on tension value, as shown in Figure 10. An increase of fiber tension causes an increase of marcel shape ratio G up to 70 N, while above 70N it shows an inverse trend. The tension value of 70N seems to be the best choice. The quality decrease connected with the tension increase, despite the improvement of the fibers alignment and compactness related to tension value increase, is due to curing problems. A tension value higher than 70 N implies a reduction of the ring section area due to the involved high compacting force. In this way the cross section of the die, that is closed on the mandrel at the end of winding process, is greater than wound part cross section. Therefore, the die can not apply to the wound part the load needed to limit deformations involved in curing process. Therefore, redesigning the die cross section by reducing its dimensions results necessary. An increase of deposition speed causes a not relevant decrease of marcel shape ratio G and the part maintains the same score mostly equal to 1 (see Figure 11).

Delamination maximum length L is not significantly influenced by anyone of the two considered process parameters, tension and deposition speed, as shown in Table 4 and in Figure 12. The parts maintain a score mostly equal to 1 (see Figure 13).

Finally, part score due to porosity remains the same (equal to 1) even if the deposition speed and/or tension value increase.

The obtained results of marcel shape ratio, delamination and porosity present a low variance: it is due to the high winding repeatability of the new cell.

Figure 10. Influence of deposition speed and roving tension on marcel shape ratio G (Main Effect Plot)

Figure 11. Frequency of part scores 1 or 2 connected with marcel shape ratio G

Table 4. ANOVA results for delamination maximum length

Source	DF	SS	MS	F	p-value
deposition speed	1	0.1452	0.1452	0.92	0.356
tension	4	1.9709	0.4927	3.12	0.056
deposition speed*tension	4	0.0394	0.0098	0.06	0.992
error	12	1.8933	0.1578		
Total	21				

Figure 12. Influence of roving tension and deposition speed on delamination maximum length (Main Effect Plot)

All the values of the part quality scores monitoring the presence of marcel, delaminations and porosity belong to the range 1÷2; so all the corresponding benchmarks are considered acceptable by aeronautic industry and all the considered process conditions manufacture acceptable benchmarks. The best results have been carried out with a tension value of 70N for any value of the deposition speed. Once redesigned the die and solved the induced vibrations problem, it will be possible to industrially use the highest value of tension (90N) and, then, to investigate the possibility to increase them further.

Figure 13. Frequency of part score 1 or 2 connected with delamination maximum length

Finally, pinchings e wrinkles are not appeared on benchmark boundaries for all process conditions. Comparing the obtained results with those due to parts manufactured by a cartesian filament winding cell [16], it is possible to underline that the new cell, shown in this paper, allows to improve the quality of the manufactured parts, despite the increase of the deposition speed, once fixed the roving tension value, since the part quality does not result significantly influenced by deposition speed. The new cell allows to use a deposition speed of 6000 mm/min producing an average part quality of about 3.8 mm as marcel shape ratio G and 2.52 mm as maximum delamination length, while the Cartesian one winds the same part with a quality of about 3 mm as marcel shape ratio G and 5.5 mm as maximum delamination length for a deposition speed of 4800 mm/min. Therefore, it will be possible in the future to further increase the deposition speed over 6000 mm/min.

The roving tension seems to influence the quality of parts, manufactured by both the cartesian and the new cells, through a similar trend, even if the values of quality parameters (marcel shape ratio and maximum delamination length) for the new cell are on an average lower than those obtained by the cartesian one.

The new cell presents the values of the quality parameters that are characterized by a variance lower than those connected to the results of the cartesian cell and, therefore, the new cell has a repeatability higher than that of cartesian one.

The new cell manufactures benchmarks characterized by a quality score on an average lower than those due to cartesian one. In fact, the quality score of parts range between 2 and 1 for the new cell and between 3 and 1 for cartesian cell.

If we compare the values of the obtained quality parameters obtained for the different values of tension, by using the largest considered value of the deposition speed for both the Cartesian cell (3200 mm/min) and the new cell (6000 mm/min), we obtain an improvement of part quality for every process conditions, as shown in Figures 14-15.

CONCLUSIONS

The present paper shows the evaluation of the performances of a new manufacturing cell, composed of an anthropomorphic robot opportunely equipped with an unique and innovative device and a

winding die, for filament winding of complex shape composite parts. The new cell has proved to be able to manufacture composite parts of high quality, i.e. parts characterized by high values of marcel shape ratio and by low values of delamination maximum length, by means of high values of deposition speed and roving tension. Therefore, it involves short manufacturing time and it allows to better control the fibres alignment inside the manufacturing parts. Moreover, it has a high repeatability in part winding. Finally, the new cell has demonstrated to improve the part quality with respect to Cartesian cell.

Figure 14. Marcel shape ratio G vs. roving tension with a deposition speed of 4800 mm/min for the Cartesian cell and 6000 mm/min for the new cell

Figure 15. Delamination maximum length vs. roving tension with a deposition speed of 4800 mm/min for the Cartesian cell and 6000 mm/min for the new cell

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